

A Three-Dimensional Finite Element Deformation Analysis of Plain Weave Woven Composite Subjected to Tensile Load

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SUMMARY: A three-dimensional displacement based finite element (FEM) analysis of the deformation of plain weave woven composite is performed to analyze the deformation behavior subjected to tensile loading. Two commercial FEM packages (ABAQUS[®] and IDEAS[®]) are used to check accuracy of the predicted data. The displacement field predicted by these two packages matched with each other with in less than one percent. Thus, displacement based commercial FEM packages, although may not provide accurate stress field for woven composites near the yarn crimping location, however, appear to provide reliable displacement field. It is inferred from the predicted displacement field that, even the composite is subjected to pure tension, the woven yarns induce twisting action in the composite. Further, if the composite is symmetrically stacked together, the yarns aligned in the applied load direction tend to delaminate from each other at their contact location.

KEYWORDS: plain weave, woven fabric composite, three-dimensional analysis, finite element analysis

INTRODUCTION

The use of fiber preforms in composites manufacturing, instead of the traditional unidirectional prepregs, has been proven to provide low-cost composite parts. Moreover, complex geometry or contoured parts, which are difficult to make from unidirectional composites, can conveniently be made with fiber preforms. The two-dimensional woven fabric (textile) of fiber tows is known to be one of the most widely used fiber preforms in producing structural composite parts. To achieve the optimum structural properties of these parts, there is a need to develop a basic understanding of deformation characteristics and failure mechanisms of woven composites.

There have been numerous studies for predicting the stiffness of fabric (woven) composites. However, the deformation characteristics and failure mechanism of this class of composites are not well understood. Several models exist in the literature for

predicting the stiffness of woven composites, such as Zhang [1], Naik [2], Hahn [3], Marrey [4], etc., to cite a few. Chou and Ko [5] provided a broad overview of this class of composites. However, the deformation behaviors of woven composites are not well investigated. In the vicinity of yarn crimping of woven fabric (woven) architecture, two perpendicular yarns crimp over and under to each other. Due to the perpendicular yarn crimping, even under the application of simple unidirectional load, the stresses in the vicinity of the yarn crimping are three-dimensional (Whitcomb [6], Cox [7]). Hence, two-dimensional stress analysis is not expected to offer a basic understanding of the failure mechanism of this material.

A representative volume element (RVE) of a plain weave woven composite is shown in Figure 1. *In situ* observation of failure initiation of woven composites reveals [8,9] that the failure in woven composites in general initiates in the vicinity of two perpendicular yarns crimping over and under to each other, also known as intertwine location (Figure 1). At the yarn-intertwine location there exist a matrix rich region, which attributes to the local stress field influencing the failure initiation process. Further, due to varying thickness of the matrix region and its modulus being much lower than that of the neighboring yarns, the commercially available displacement based finite element methods (FEM) fail to predict reliable stress field in the vicinity of the yarn crimping (yarn-intertwine) location. In displacement based FEM, the stress field is derived from the displacement field and the three-dimensional equilibrium equation is not explicitly satisfied. Further, the commercial FEM, being generally a displacement-based model, is not expected to provide reliable stress field at the vicinity of yarn crimping location, a location of high stress and strain gradients. However, in our experience, commercial FEM predicts quite reliable displacement field for woven composites. Thus, in absence of a reliable working stress prediction model, at present, our focus is to study the deformation behavior (using displacement prediction) of a plain weave composite by using commercial FEM packages. The objective of this study is to use the deformation characteristics to gain an insight towards understanding the failure mechanism of woven composites. In this work, two FEM packages (ABAQUS[®] and IDEAS[®]) are used to study the three-dimensional deformation behavior a plain weave composite. We developed the geometry of the FEM model by recognizing the subregions of the yarns and matrix regions separately, assigning respective materials properties, and then interfacing these subregions together. The development of the model geometry and the deformation behavior observed subjected to a tensile loading is presented below.

MODEL DEVELOPMENT

The yarns and the matrix regions of the model are divided into six subregions. The subregions of the four yarns of the RVE are defined as Subregions 1-4. The lower and upper matrix regions are defined as Subregions 5 and 6. The respective locations of the subregions in the RVE are shown in Figure 1. The lower and upper boundary of a Subregion are denoted as $h_1^{(I)}$ and $h_2^{(I)}$ respectively, where the subscript I denotes Subregion I. The expressions for the Subregion boundaries are given in Appendix.

Each Subregion is modeled with 8-noded solid elements. In order to obtain a reliable result, each Subregion is discretized into two layers in the thickness direction. The

interface displacement continuity of the Subregions is enforced by merging the surface nodes at the interface of the adjacent Subregions. To simulate the tensile loading, the boundary condition for the RVE is given below.

1. surface $x=0$, $u=0$
2. surface $y=0$, $v=0$
3. surface $z=0$, $w=0$
4. surface $y=C_f$, $v=0$
5. surface $x=C_w$, $u=U_a$ (U_a is the applied displacement)
6. surface $z=2(t_w+t_f)$ is traction free

The above boundary conditions simulate a case where two layers of symmetrically stacked plain weave composite is subjected to a tensile strain in the warp direction with lateral constraint (strain in the y -direction is kept at zero). In other words, to keep the study to somewhat simple, the strain in the y -direction due to the Poisson's ratio is not induced in this study. The effect of the Poisson's ratio can be added later to this result by a linear superposition.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The plain weave composite considered in this study is made with graphite/epoxy (AS4/3501-6) with yarn fiber volume fraction of 0.60. The objective of this study, as mentioned before, is to analyze the deformation behavior the RVE of a plain weave composite subjected to a tensile loading. The analysis of the deformation field is expected to provide us an insight towards understanding the failure initiation process. In order to analyze the deformation behavior and how the Subregions (yarns) deform with respect to one another, the three displacement components are plotted at several locations on the vertical boundary surfaces. In Figures 2 and 3 the values of displacement u are plotted for different x locations on the two-boundary surfaces parallel to the y -plane. The applied displacement, U_a , and thickness, $2(t_w+t_f)$ normalize the values of the abscissa (displacement u) and ordinate (thickness), of the RVE, respectively. For $x/C_w = 0$, the displacement along this vertical line (i.e., $x=0$) is zero, which is the imposed boundary condition. Also, for $x/C_w = 1$, the displacement u along this vertical line ($x=C_w$) is uniform, which is the applied boundary displacement. For other values of x/C_w (0.1 to 0.9), the values of the displacement u are shown in Figure 2. It is to note that Subregion 1 (Yarn 1) occupies the lower half of the ordinate at $x/C_w = 0$, then gradually weaves to occupy the upper half of the ordinate at $x/C_w = 1.0$ (see Figure 1). Keeping in mind the region of the surface in Figure 1 that Subregion 1 occupies, Figure 2 reveals that the lower surface of Subregion 1 (Yarn 1) stretches more than its upper surface for the segment $x/C_w = 0.0$ to 0.5. For $x/C_w = 0.5$ to 1.0, its upper surface stretches more than the lower surface. In other words, Yarn 1 (which is a warp yarn aligned in the direction of the applied load) concaves upwards for the segment $x/C_w = 0.0$ to 0.5, then it concaves downward for the segment $x/C_w = 0.5$ to 1.0. Thus, although the RVE (i.e., the plain weave composite) is overall subjected to a pure tensile load, Yarn 1 is inducing a twist to the composite. A similar phenomenon is also observed in Figure 3, where Subregion 4 (Yarn 4) concaves downward for the segment $x/C_w = 0.0$ to 0.5, and then concaves

upward for the segment $x/C_w = 0.5$ to 1.0 . Here also Yarn 4 is inducing a twist to the composite in an opposite direction than that of Yarn 1. A similar set of values for displacement v is also obtained, however, is not presented here, to keep the length of this paper somewhat brief.

Figure 4 and 5 show the values of displacement w (displacement in the thickness direction). The values of displacement w in Figures 4 and 5 are plotted in the same manner as that in Figures 2 and 3. It is to note that a negative value in w indicates a thickness reduction of the composite and a positive value in w indicates a thickness increase. Figure 4 reveals that a small segment near $x/C_w = 0.0$, there is an increase in thickness. It should be noted that near $x/C_w = 0.0$ Yarn 1 occupies the lower half of the composite. At other values of x/C_w , there is significant decrease in thickness of the composite, greatest decrease being near $x/C_w = 1.0$, where Yarn 1 occupies the upper half of the composites accompanied by Yarn 2 occupying the lower half aligned in y -direction. Physically, this implies that if we have two layers of plain weave composite symmetrically stacked together subjected to a tensile loading with upper and lower boundary surfaces of the composite constrained to flat surfaces, then, location near $x/C_w = 1.0$ (on $y=0$ plane), would tend to delaminate. It is worth to mention that, as Figure 1 reveals, for symmetrically stacked layers $x/C_w = 1.0$ (on $y=0$ plane) is the location of contact of the yarns aligned in the applied load direction. Near $x/C_w = 0.0$ (on $y=0$ plane), the composite would remain in contact (in compression). A similar inference can also be made from Figure 5 at locations near $x/C_w = 0.0$ and 1.0 (on $y=C_f$ plane), respectively. Thus, for symmetrically stacked-up plain weave composite layers subjected to tensile load, yarns aligned in the applied load direction tend to delaminate from each other at the location of their contact.

CONCLUSION

A three-dimensional finite element analysis of the deformation of plain weave woven composite is performed to analyze the deformation behavior subjected to tensile loading. Two commercial FEM packages (ABAQUS[®] and IDEAS[®]) are used to check accuracy of the predicted data. The displacement field predicted by these two packages matched with each other with in less than one percent. It is inferred from the predicted displacement field that, even the composite is subjected to pure tension, the woven yarns induce twisting action in the composite. Further, if the composite is symmetrically stacked together, the yarns aligned in the applied load direction tend to delaminate from each other at their contact location.

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Figure 1. Representative Volume Element (RVE) of a plain weave composites.

Figure 2. Displacement u at several locations on surface y = 0.

Figure 3. Displacement u at several locations on surface $y = C_f$.

Figure 4. Displacement w at several locations on surface y = 0.

Figure 5. Displacement w at several locations on surface $y = C_f$.

APPENDIX A

$$h_1^{(1)} = t_f \left(1 - \cos \frac{\pi x}{C_w} \right) + t_w \left(1 - \cos \frac{\pi y}{C_f} \right); \quad 0 \leq x \leq C_w, 0 \leq y \leq \frac{C_f}{2}$$

$$h_2^{(1)} = t_f \left(1 - \cos \frac{\pi x}{C_w} \right) + t_w \left(1 + \cos \frac{\pi y}{C_f} \right); \quad 0 \leq x \leq C_w, 0 \leq y \leq \frac{C_f}{2}$$

$$h_1^{(2)} = t_f \left(1 + \cos \frac{\pi x}{C_w} \right) + t_w \left(1 - \cos \frac{\pi y}{C_f} \right); \quad \frac{C_w}{2} \leq x \leq C_w, 0 \leq y \leq C_f$$

$$h_2^{(2)} = t_f \left(1 - \cos \frac{\pi x}{C_w} \right) + t_w \left(1 - \cos \frac{\pi y}{C_f} \right); \quad \frac{C_w}{2} \leq x \leq C_w, 0 \leq y \leq C_f$$

$$h_1^{(3)} = t_f \left(1 - \cos \frac{\pi x}{C_w} \right) + t_w \left(1 + \cos \frac{\pi y}{C_f} \right); \quad 0 \leq x \leq \frac{C_w}{2}, 0 \leq y \leq C_f$$

$$h_2^{(3)} = t_f \left(1 + \cos \frac{\pi x}{C_w} \right) + t_w \left(1 + \cos \frac{\pi y}{C_f} \right); \quad 0 \leq x \leq \frac{C_w}{2}, 0 \leq y \leq C_f$$

$$h_1^{(4)} = t_f \left(1 + \cos \frac{\pi x}{C_w} \right) + t_w \left(1 + \cos \frac{\pi y}{C_f} \right); \quad 0 \leq x \leq C_w, \frac{C_f}{2} \leq y \leq C_f$$

$$h_2^{(4)} = t_f \left(1 + \cos \frac{\pi x}{C_w} \right) + t_w \left(1 - \cos \frac{\pi y}{C_f} \right); \quad 0 \leq x \leq C_w, \frac{C_f}{2} \leq y \leq C_f$$

$$h_1^{(5)} = 0; \quad 0 \leq x \leq C_w, 0 \leq y \leq C_f$$

$$h_2^{(5)} = t_f \left(1 - \cos \frac{\pi x}{C_w} \right) + t_w \left(1 - \cos \frac{\pi y}{C_f} \right); \quad 0 \leq x \leq \frac{C_w}{2}, 0 \leq y \leq \frac{C_f}{2}$$

$$h_2^{(5)} = t_f \left(1 + \cos \frac{\pi x}{C_w} \right) + t_w \left(1 - \cos \frac{\pi y}{C_f} \right); \quad \frac{C_w}{2} \leq x \leq C_w, 0 \leq y \leq \frac{C_f}{2}$$

$$h_2^{(5)} = t_f \left(1 - \cos \frac{\pi x}{C_w} \right) + t_w \left(1 + \cos \frac{\pi y}{C_f} \right); \quad 0 \leq x \leq \frac{C_w}{2}, \frac{C_f}{2} \leq y \leq C_f$$

$$h_2^{(5)} = t_f \left(1 + \cos \frac{\pi x}{C_w} \right) + t_w \left(1 + \cos \frac{\pi y}{C_f} \right); \quad \frac{C_w}{2} \leq x \leq C_w, \frac{C_f}{2} \leq y \leq C_f$$

$$\begin{aligned}
h_1^{(6)} &= t_f \left(1 + \cos \frac{\pi x}{C_w} \right) + t_w \left(1 + \cos \frac{\pi y}{C_f} \right) ; \quad 0 \leq x \leq \frac{C_w}{2}, 0 \leq y \leq \frac{C_f}{2} \\
h_1^{(6)} &= t_f \left(1 - \cos \frac{\pi x}{C_w} \right) + t_w \left(1 + \cos \frac{\pi y}{C_f} \right) ; \quad \frac{C_w}{2} \leq x \leq C_w, 0 \leq y \leq \frac{C_f}{2} \\
h_1^{(6)} &= t_f \left(1 + \cos \frac{\pi x}{C_w} \right) + t_w \left(1 - \cos \frac{\pi y}{C_f} \right) ; \quad 0 \leq x \leq \frac{C_w}{2}, \frac{C_f}{2} \leq y \leq C_f \\
h_1^{(6)} &= t_f \left(1 - \cos \frac{\pi x}{C_w} \right) + t_w \left(1 - \cos \frac{\pi y}{C_f} \right) ; \quad \frac{C_w}{2} \leq x \leq C_w, \frac{C_f}{2} \leq y \leq C_f \\
h_1^{(6)} &= 2(t_f + t_w) ; \quad 0 \leq x \leq C_w, 0 \leq y \leq C_f
\end{aligned}$$